

Temple of Ištar (Emašmaš) at Nineveh

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Entry tags: Temple, Mesopotamian Religions, Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Assyrian Religions, Polytheistic, Mesopotamian Religion, Religious Place, Shrine, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult

The temple of Ištar is located atop the Kouyunjik mound of ancient Nineveh, which is bounded by the Tigris river to the west and surrounded by the modern city of Mosul in Northern Iraq. By the second millennium BCE, it was referred to as Emašmaš. It is possible this name may in fact refer to a group of structures containing shrines to various deities in the immediate vicinity of the main temple. There is also a ziggurat dedicated to Ištar thought to be located southwest of Emašmaš complex. According to Šamši-Adad I (r.1808-1776 BCE), a temple was first built to Ištar in Nineveh by the Akkadian ruler Maništušu, which he then rebuilt on a monumental scale. There is limited archaeological evidence of earlier structures dated to the 3rd millennium BCE beneath the large platform Šamši-Adad built his new temple upon, one of which could have been built by Maništušu. From this point the temple entered into a long history of continued use, with many subsequent phases of reconstruction and renovation. These phases are well-attested for the Middle Assyrian and Neo-Assyrian periods, where foundation inscriptions, bricks and wall-pegs found in the main temple area name and/or describe the building efforts of multiple kings, in particular: Aššur-uballiṭ I (r.1363-1328 BCE), Shalmaneser I (r.1263-1234 BCE), Tukulti-Ninurta I (r.1233-1197 BCE), Aššurnaširpal II (r. 883-859 BCE), Sennacherib (r.704-681 BCE), and Aššurbanipal (r. 668-631 BCE). There may have been earlier Old Assyrian/Babylonian and Mittani presence at Kouyunjik as well, but it is unclear to what extent Nineveh was directly incorporated into these polities. Limited cuneiform records and archaeological evidence do exist pertaining to activities at Nineveh from these periods; for instance, Hammurapi of Babylon mentions his pious works in Emašmaš on his famous stele. Depending on who controlled Nineveh at the time, the goddess occupying the temple may have been equated with Šauška, a Hurrian goddess (early 2nd millennium BCE), Mullissu, the wife of Aššur (Neo-Assyrian period), or with Sumerian Inana or Ninlil. As the daughter of Šin and sister to Šamaš, Ištar is a main goddess of the Mesopotamian pantheon, with roles in war, fertility/sex, and nature. The temple itself is not fully excavated due to surface erosion on its eastern side, and understanding its stratigraphy is quite difficult, considering that areas of the temple proper had been demolished and rebuilt at variable depths throughout its history. In general, the temple was a rectangular building built upon a mudbrick platform, containing an inner and outer courtyard, the outer of which was bounded by a series of rooms on its northwest, southwest, and southeast sides. Its main entrance is thought to be from the northwest via a monumental gate flanked with stone statues of lions, which are the attribute animal of Ištar. As collateral damage in the collapse of the Neo-Assyrian empire in 612 BCE, the temple was extensively burned, its fragmented materials used for building later structures on the site.

Date Range: 1800 BCE - 612 BCE

Region: Kouyunjik mound, Nineveh

Region tags: Middle East, Northern Iraq, Iraq

The polygon shows the general area of the Emašmaš temple complex between the North Palace of Aššurbanipal and the Southwest Palace of Sennacherib.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Thompson, R.C., and R.W. Hamilton. The British Museum Excavations on the Temple of Ishtar at Nineveh, 1930-1. *Annals of Archaeology and Anthropology* Vol XIX, Nos. 3-4, 1932.
- Source 2: Reade, J.E. "The Ishtar Temple at Nineveh." *Iraq* 67, no. 1 (2005): 347-90.
- Source 3: Reade, J.E. "Ninive (Nineveh)." In *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie*, 9:388-433, 2000.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/riao/index.html>
- Source 1 Description: The Royal Inscriptions of Assyria online Project. Digitized and annotated editions of all known Akkadian and Sumerian royal inscriptions from Assyria.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Reference: Reade, J.E.. "Ninive (nineveh)". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 9 (2000): 388-433. p.393-4

Type of excavation:

– Pre-modern

Notes: The area of the Ištar temple on the Kouyunjik mound had some early archaeological activity, funded in large part by the British Museum. This was conducted by Christian Rassam (1851-2), Hormudz Rassam (1852-4, 1878-80), George Smith (1873-4) and Leonard King and Reginald Campbell Thompson (1903-5).

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: From 1927-32, R. Campbell Thompson and colleagues excavated the temple to its current extent.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Notes: From roughly 2015-2016, Daesh/Islamic State looted and destroyed large areas of the Kouyunjik mound, particularly the Palace of Sennacherib, which is immediately adjacent to the Emašmaš temple complex.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

– Other [specify]: The mound of Kouyunjik is 25-30 meters higher than the rest of the ancient city of Nineveh, located in its west-central sector.

– Water source

– Other [specify]: Nineveh is located on the eastern side of the Tigris river, and the city itself is bisected by the Khosr river, which is a tributary of the Tigris.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The Ištar temple (Emašmaš) complex is adjacent to the Nabû temple and between the

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The temple has not been completely excavated. The name 'Emašmaš' may refer to a group of structures, including shrines to various deities. The presumably nearby Kidmuri temple may have been included under this title, and there was apparently also a shrine to Gula somewhere on Kouyunjik mound. The late 3rd/early 2nd millennium version of the temple (pre-Šamši-Adad I) may have been a single shrine to Ištar, but it is impossible to know since excavations could not reach that level in all areas of the temple due to state of preservation/immediate topography. The 2nd and 1st millennium versions of the temple roughly preserved a rectangular layout of some 55m wide and 110 m long, with a monumental entrance to the southwest.

A group of structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: see above note under 'a single structure'

A group of features:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Ištar temple was continuously refurbished throughout its almost two millennia existence. Although Šamši-Adad I built the temple whose form was largely respected until 612 BCE, he mentions that he restored a temple to Ištar initially built by the Akkadian king Maništušu, known as the é-me-nu-è (RIMA 1 A.O.39.2). Two earthquakes damaged the temple during the Middle Assyrian period, which then necessitated restorations by Shalmaneser I and Aššur-reš-iši I (r. 1132-1115 BCE). Inscribed wall pegs and bricks scattered about the site also allude to restorations and refurbishment undertaken by Aššur-uballiṭ I, Tukulti-Ninurta I, and Šamši-Adad IV. In the Neo-Assyrian period, Aššurnaširpal II did significant renovations of the temple.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: see above notes on 'a single structure'

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Communal and Individual

Notes: Fragments of vessels (and whole vessels) were found in multiple phases of the temple which are thought to have once held scented oils, as well as terracotta and lead plaques of nude females, which suggest that ritual activities and dedication took place at the site. In addition, the cult statue of Ištar periodically left Emašmaš to travel to her bīt akītu somewhere in the lower city of Nineveh (or perhaps still on the Kouyunjik mound, we do not know exactly where this was located). This would have been a communal, public activity.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: see above sub-note under 'group of features'

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: The Ištar temple was burned, presumably in 612 BCE during the collapse of the Neo-Assyrian empire. Ash layers ranging in 31-123 cm were found inside and outside of the temple.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–For political reasons

–As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: The temple sustained damage from earthquakes twice in its recorded history, which then required restorations.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The temple is dedicated to Ištar of Nineveh. By the late Middle Assyrian period into the Neo-Assyrian period, she also had counterparts in Aššur and Arbela, each with their own temples.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there was certainly a 'temple to Ištar', the larger Emašmaš complex may have included the Kidmuri temple and a shrine to Gula (and possibly other small shrines).

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: In royal inscriptions, Assyrian kings often describe temple building in the first-person without naming specific groups of people. However, we know that the carving of images upon wall panels lining temples and palaces required specialized craftspeople. The Aššurnaširpal II version of the temple had wall panels showing scenes of tribute lining parts of the temple interior, which would have required skilled labor.

– Slaves

– Corvee labourers

– Captured enemies

– Other [specify]: It is also possible that building the actual structure required the labor of slaves, corvee labourers, and/or captured enemies. In the Neo-Assyrian period, kings would deport large groups of people from conquered areas, and some of these individuals were likely conscripted in building works.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: Temple building (and restoration) was considered an important task for Mesopotamia kings to consistently fulfill in order to show their piety and devotion to the gods/their patron god(s).

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's not clear if the temple was connected to the adjacent ziggurat. The Ištar temple was perhaps part of a larger temple complex (Emašmaš) housing other goddesses.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The temple has not been completely excavated, and the southeastern side in particular is very denuded. It is postulated to have been at least 55 meters in width and at least 106 meters in length.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The walls of the temple originally built by Šamši-Adad I and renovated by his successors have not survived to any significant height. We do not know the true height of the temple walls in any period. The earlier building preserved underneath the Šamši-Adad version of the temple did have wall heights preserved up to 2.5 meters.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: packed mudbrick platform

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: While we do not know the exact type of wood used in the Iṣtar temple's construction, we do know that wood was used, and it is likely this wood was imported. Cedar was particularly prized as building materials for Mesopotamian palaces and temples, the main source of which was located in the Northern Levant.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The lions flanking the northwestern entrance into the temple complex were made of stone. Limited evidence of paving stones.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: mud-brick and worked stone

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: We do not know much about the decoration of the temple. There is limited archaeological evidence (see below in sub-sections) and many Middle and Neo-Assyrian kings did not talk about specific decorative refurbishments, only that they rebuilt or renovated (parts of) the temple/Emašmaš itself. A fragmentary inscription of Aššurbanipal found during Thompson's excavations in the southeastern area of the temple states that the king decorated the gates and shrines of Emašmaš with silver and gold (Fuchs 1996, 291).

Reference: Fuchs, A.. "Die Inschrift Vom Ištar-tempel". In Beiträge Zum Inschriftenwerk Assurbanipals, 258–96. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 1996.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Stone lions were apparently located at the northwestern gateway into the temple as well as along its facade. It is unclear whether the external walls of the temple had any type of niched decoration. Wall-pegs, glazed tiles and stamped bricks could have also adorned the exterior facade of the temple, but it is impossible to deduce due to the lack of preserved walls. Freestanding monuments or obelisks could have also formed part of the external visual program

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: From the Neo-Assyrian phase of the temple: in the scattered fill of internal courtyard, wall-pegs/cones, stamped bricks, and glazed tiles with fragments of narrative scenes were found. In squares IO, fragmentary wall reliefs of tribute processions are

preserved up to the feet. Other fragments of wall panels had an inscription of Aššurnaširpal II which extolled the king's military prowess and his procurement of wood for the roof of the temple.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A 9th century glazed tile shows a female garbed with weapons and a crown being followed by an attendant. This could be Ištar herself, or perhaps an Assyrian Queen (see Reade 2005, 351).

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The remains of 9th century BCE gypsum wall panels shows pairs of feet in a row in a scene of tribute.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Fragments of a wall panel found outside the area of the northwestern wall depict hunting scenes (lion and bull). Reade (2005, 378) argues that these were originally from Aššurnaširpal II's 9th century BCE version of the Ištar temple.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is probable that dedicated statues of Assyrian royalty and members of their court once inhabited internal areas of the Emašmaš complex. Excavators found the stone head of a female (British Museum # 135106) inside the temple.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If there were, none have survived and there are no extant writings about them.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: see above comment

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Tribute scene involving procession of tribute-bearers, and potentially hunting scenes, although these were found fragmented and scattered outside the temple proper.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The inscription of Aššurnāṣirpal II (883-859 BCE) found on fragmentary wall reliefs describes his rebuilding of Emašmaš and its updated adornment with a new timber roof as well as his many military victories.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not enough visual evidence has survived to answer this question.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not enough of the visual program of the Ištar temple to survives to know whether supernatural beings were also depicted on its walls (as, for example, at the Ninurta temple at Nimrud).

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: The cult statue of Ištar of Nineveh does not survive, but we know it once existed, and it would have been periodically taken out of the temple for ritual processions.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– Yes

Notes: Due to the relative ephemerality of the archaeological record at this location, there are few examples of material offerings. However, there are a few possibilities that might have been considered material offerings: one, a grouping of stone fragments attributed to Shalmaneser III (858-824 BCE) with an inscribed dedication to Ištar, multiple terracotta images of naked and clothed women from the 3rd - 1st millenniums, as well as glass and faience beads from the Mittani period (mid 2nd millennium) along with beads from the earlier structure beneath the Šamši-Adad I version of the temple. The famous copper head of an Akkadian ruler (Iraq Museum # 11331) was also found in

the temple precinct.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:
– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that the Ištar temple space had to remain ritually clean but we do not have any texts to confirm this specific case.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– Yes

Notes: see comments under 'General Variables- Structures Present'

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Yes

Notes: We don't know much about temple administration or cult at Emašmaš. There were likely temple attendants who had specific roles in the everyday operating of the temple.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: The cult state of Ištar (and others if they were present in the Emašmaš complex) would have journeyed out from her shrine and traveled to her akītu-house. This would have been a multi-day festival. By the Neo-Assyrian period, the king would be expected to participate in these festivities.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: see above note on festivals

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: multiple times per year

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: While we don't know the exact specialists who were connected with the Emašmaš in particular, we do know that there were male and female individuals connected with the veneration of Ištar and her temple cult. For male roles, see *assinnu* and *kurgarrû*; for female roles, see *ištarītu*, *kezertu*, *šamhatu*, *harimtu*. More information about these roles and their appearances in Mesopotamian history can be found via the Chicago Assyrian Dictionary.

Reference: Wilcke, C.. "Inanna/ištar". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 5 (1980): 74–89. p.85-6

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:
– Yes

Notes: The temple would have had its own staff.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:
– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The temple contained scholarly tablets and letters from the Uruk and Old Babylonian periods. Tablets from later periods were also found scattered nearby, including the Tukulti-Ninurta Epic (Middle Assyrian) and temple records (Neo-Assyrian), as well as a temple loan from the mid 7th-century BCE (K 318). There are also foundation documents found in disturbed contexts around the temple from various Assyrian rulers.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

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